

GRAMMATICAL SPECIFICITY OF NEWSPAPER HEADLINE TRANSLATION (BASED ON HEADLINES FROM NEWSPAPER «THE GUARDIANS»)

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ABSTRACT

The given publication work is aimed at revealing the fact that translating press works has its own grammar features. The headline is an indispensable and integral part of any newspaper and newspaper article. This is the utmost actual and generally first thing that a reader sees and further understands whether he should read the article disposed. It is particularly the title that draws the reader's attention to the article contents.

The first fact should be considered that press translation has its own difficulties. The headline is an indispensable and integral part of any newspaper and newspaper article. This is the utmost actual and generally first thing that a reader sees and further understands whether he should read the article disposed. It is particularly the title that draws the reader's attention to the article contents. Quite often, while translating a headline from English into Uzbek, various kinds of transformations are used. One of the classifications was proposed by the Russian Professor V.N.Komissarov. The linguist divides translation transformations into three groups: lexical, grammatical and lexical-grammatical. To each group of transformations he relates various translation techniques. Thus, lexical transformations include transcription and transliteration, calques, and lexical-semantic replacements (specification, generalization, modulation). Grammatical transformations are formed by grammatical replacements, syntactic analogy, the division of sentences and sentence integration. The following methods belong to lexical-grammatical transformations: antonymic translation, explication, compensation [1, p.172–173]. This classification was the basis for the analysis. Such types of transformations as permutations, additions and omissions were taken into consideration, since, as it was revealed, when translating headlines they are used no less often than other types of transformations identified by V.N.Komissarov. In this article we will discuss in detail the translation transformations used to deliver the headlines of “The Guardian” newspaper into Uzbek. Each type of transformation will be supported by several examples from different headings. Newspaper headlines are of great importance in modern life as they perform the task of attracting the reader's attention and conveying essential information at the same time. In this work, we review in detail the types of translation transformations by which the English-language titles are translated. Considerable attention is paid to particular examples of

headlines and the identification of their translation specifics. Based on the study of the features of the newspaper headlines translation, the most frequently used transformations in the translation into Uzbek are identified and detailed statistics are given. V.N.Komissarov includes transcription, transliteration, calque, specification, generalization and modulation into lexical transformations group. In the course of the study, each of the varieties was more or less singled out among the considered headlines of “The Guardian” newspaper. In this case, the least common transformations were transliteration, calque and modulation, while transcription was the most frequent transformation. In total 31 lexical transformations were allocated of 301 identified case which is 10%. Each specific variety of lexical transformations will be discussed further. Thus, in transcription and transliteration the form of a lexical unit in the source language is transmitted using the letters of the translating language: in transcription the sound form is transmitted, in transliteration — the graphic form. One can certainly admit that the boundaries between these two types of lexical transformations are rather fuzzy, as it is commonly known that they are frequently used together in translation. Nevertheless, within the framework of the analysed 104 headlines, it turns to be clear that a greater preference is given to the transmission of the sound form of a foreign word, i. e. its transcription. In the course of the work, 10 newspaper headlines were identified, in the translation of which transcription of individual words was used. Transliteration was applied in the translation of only two titles. In accordance with this, the percentage between them is distributed as follows: transcription — 32% of all identified cases of lexical transformations, transliteration — 6%. Actually the names of public figures, different names, political events, etc. are normally transcribed and transliterated in the translation. Many of them eventually take hold and become accepted in the translation, therefore, in this paper only those names that are unlikely to be widely spread were considered. One can refer to the following title: “Russian prosecutors bring fresh charges against Kremlin critic Bill Browder”. At the end of the headline the name of the Kremlin critic is mentioned. As mentioned earlier, transliteration was applied to the translation of two English headlines. This type of lexical transformation was applied in combination with the transcription method. Calque is the transfer of the lexical unit of the original by replacing its constituent parts with the corresponding parts in the translating language. Along with transliteration, the calque transformation was highlighted only in two translated newspaper headlines, which also accounts for 6% of all identified cases of lexical transformations. The first title, as a result of the translation of which a calque was applied, was the following: “UK targets Eurovision viewers to counter Russia’s “infowars”. The following translation was provided: „ Buyuk Britaniya „ Yevrovideniya” tamoshabinlari Rossiyaning informatsion urushlariga qarshi turmoqchi”. Hence the phrase “infowars” is informatsion urushlar, i.e. each part of the original word has been respectively translated into Uzbek: info — informatsion, wars — urushlar. Another headline, in which one can observe a word translated by means of calque, is “At a time of permanent cyberwar, the UK must stand firm against Russia”. In this case, the calque was applied to the word “cyberwar”, later translated as kiberurush . The method of specification implies the replacement of a foreign word with a broad meaning by a word in a translating language with a narrower meaning. While generalizing, the opposite replacement occurs: a word with a narrow meaning in the source language is transmitted by a word with a wide meaning in the

target language. The transformations of specification and generalization became the second most frequently used lexical transformations after transcription in the translation of newspaper headlines. The study revealed seven cases of the use of specification and seven cases of the use of generalization. When translating the title, the translator applies specification to the phrase “chemical weapons vote”. The literal translation of the phrase could be as follows: yadroviy qurollarga ovoz berish. However, the translator decides to apply the specification, which in turn leads to the replacement of the attribute by the adverbial modifier. Thus, the place of the vote referred to in the headline is specified, since O3XO is Organization for the prohibition of chemical weapons. When translating the headline “What could the US target in Syria and how is Russia likely to react?” specification was also used. In this example, the sentence member was replaced as well. The translator replaces the adverbial modifier “Syria” with a specified object: Suriya obyektleri. Another type of lexical transformations is modulation. It is a translation transformation in which the unit of the source language is replaced by the unit of the translating language and the meaning of the second logically follows the meaning of the first. In the course of the study, the lexical transformation modulation was found only in three headings, which is 10% of the number of all identified cases of lexical transformations. The following group of transformations to be reviewed is grammatical transformations. The discussion of their peculiarities will be raised below. Thus, some English newspaper headlines are translated into Uzbek by means of such grammatical transformation as a syntactic analogy. In this case, the translated title retains the entire set of sentence members and their sequence. It was found that as a result of the translation newspaper headlines underwent this transformation, which is one fifth of all identified cases of grammatical transformations. One example of the translation of a newspaper headline by means of syntactical assimilation is presented below: “The best way to scupper Putin and Trump? Scrap Brexit” Putin va Trampga qarshi bo’lish, Breksitdan voz kechish. While translating the headline, the sentence structure was kept. All parts of the sentence in the translated title are kept and located in the same place as in the original title.

Hence, a newspaper headline is of great importance in the newspaper discourse. It is an important part of a newspaper article and it performs a number of functions. English newspaper headlines and headlines in Uzbek differ from each other and have their own characteristics; this is why the study had the aim to identify the specifics of the translation of headlines from English into Uzbek. As a result, the objective of this work was achieved.

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